

The Fundamental aspects of mathematical physics

"Cold Fusion Modulation Trends"

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• **Keywords**

mass, dark matter, time, energy, limits, mass charge, structure, number theory, charge, function, numerical physics, number space, limits of space, cyclic structure, mass system, number nucleons.

• **Resume**

The Matter of Space, which forms the structure of space, determines the Energy of the Mass of Space. Any value of a number corresponds to the function of the contour of the numerical space of its content and expression, enclosed in the corresponding structure, consisting of quantities of numerical events, equal and unequal to each other, functionally dependent within the value of the structure of periodic numerical content, external and internal definition of the functional structure of the numerical mass, where the function is the generating energy of the content of the space of the numerical structure.

A charge containing the opposite limits of the internal and external values of the limits of space - a space enclosed by numbers that transform the linear and volumetric function - the energy of the mass structure of the interaction of counter and opposite periods of its definition.

• Introduction

The classical definition of the concept “Mass”, in its rhetorical expression, does not correspond to the actual state of “numerical” matter, or more precisely to the mathematical matrix of physical definitions. These “misconceptions” have now become the main reason before the next progress of scientific thought, after mass and energy were separated in the relative position of the well-known formula.

This forced “deception” was hastily proposed to the consciousness of the scientific community, while it was a panacea for the excited aspirations of the world community, expecting from the “magic” of science more and more “miracles” - “paradise”, the ideal well-being of its entire existence. But the events that make up the history of the past century, and even the present, show that manna from heaven is still unknown...

The cascade of world discoveries from Newton to Einstein, from the observer to the “blind” experimenter, distorted the hereditary philosophy of perceiving the picture of the World in favor of the shortage of a separate industrial product, which decides for itself the well-being of a separate society on the verge of its own destruction.

The tension of the question, how long can mass remain from energy, when scientific thought, in a state of empirical inertia of stubborn rhetoric, continues to “grind” the same results of its “neoclassical” limit between experimental experience and theory.

The absence of the naturalist is not the presence of the observer. The Global Time of perception and study of the general Laws of natural phenomena, and the justification of individual desired results obtained from experiments, is not consciousness, but the need for a relatively short artificial time of this erudition.

More and more often, individual “impulses” of the natural consciousness of scientific thought, going beyond the framework of consumer science, do not abandon attempts to refute the existing “postulates” that claim to be the general one in philosophy. First of all, this consciousness is the consciousness of the natural need for the truly fundamental data of the Nature around us in favor of its Global Time.

Any sequence, of any numerical composition, of the order of natural numbers, can be represented as a periodic fragment of the relations of the bases of the relationship of the limits of the internal and external content of the functional structure of a unit of space ($\pi/6$).

This value of defining a numerical event of linear and volumetric content determines the cyclicity between the limits of the functions of opposite values of the internal and external numerical structure. Thus, this definition characterizes the functional composition of the structure of a nucleon - a unit of the limits of a fragment of space in which the content of the proton charge number refers to the internal value, and the neutron number acquires an external value. The study of the periodicity conditions of the linear relationship between the proton and the neutron in the nucleon composition clarifies the processes of displacement by pose (π'), that is, the relationship of polar values, the main functions of the limits of the space contour.

This refers to the increase and decrease in the process of distribution of functional characteristics of protons and neutrons in the structure of the nucleon itself. In this case, the relationship of polar values, these elementary fragments, is a variable determination of the general numerical structure - the essence of the charge. Here the division and merging of the values of each taken nucleon occurs into sums of protons, neutrons, units of charges - numerical events of these sums. Thus, the linear periodicity of the number of events, as a unit of the sums of protons or neutrons in the structure of a nucleon, determines the phenomenal value of the results of the relationship (π') for each isotope of this nucleon.

To do this, each functional fragment - the mass of elementary particles in the nucleon composition - determines its quantitative units - the number of proton or neutron events relative to the main charge of the nuclear symbol.

For example, the determination of the nucleon number of any nuclear symbol occurs based on the stable mass of this nucleus. Therefore, if this is Oxygen, then its common nucleon for all isotopes will correspond to the mass number sixteen:

$$\bullet \text{nykl O}^{16} \rightarrow (15.9994 / 16) = 0.9999625$$

Therefore, the mass of mass number thirteen will be:

$$\bullet \mathbf{m}^{13} = 13\text{nykl O}^{16} = 12.9995125$$

The determination of functional fragments (**fmp** and **fmn**) occurs as a result of phase exchanges between the number of protons and the number of neutrons relative to the mass number:

$$\bullet ((\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B}) / \mathbf{A})^{-1} \leftrightarrow ((\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B}) / \mathbf{B})^{-1}; \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{mp} (1.00727647), \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{mn} (1.008665012)$$

Here, a snippet of the proton function: $\mathbf{fmp} = \text{nykl} - ((\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B}) / \mathbf{A})^{-1}$

Neutron function fragment: $\mathbf{fnn} = \mathbf{nykl} - ((\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B}) / \mathbf{B})^{-1}$

In the case of determining the real numbers of protons and neutrons for the thirteenth mass of Oxygen, the result of the solution will be as follows:

- $[\mathbf{nykl} - ((\mathbf{8mp} + \mathbf{5mn}) / \mathbf{8mp})^{-1}] / \mathbf{13}^{-1} = \mathbf{mp}'(0.999470084)$

- $[\mathbf{nykl} - ((\mathbf{8mp} + \mathbf{5mn}) / \mathbf{5mn})^{-1}] / \mathbf{13}^{-1} = \mathbf{mn}'(1.000530197)$

These data correspond to the values of the displacement pose projections of the internal and external content of the number and the number field as: $n \neq n^{-1}$.

Thus, it is possible to determine the charge unit of each functional fragment of the volumetric content for this value.

If: $\mathbf{fmp}' = [(\mathbf{8mp}' + \mathbf{5mn}') / \mathbf{8mp}'] = \mathbf{0.615058513}$

Then: $\mathbf{fnn}' = \mathbf{nykl} - \mathbf{fmp}' = \mathbf{0.384903987}$

Therefore, the unit of charge - numerical event ($\mathbf{n}^s$) or the value of the base of the reduced volume will correspond to:

- $\mathbf{n}^s(\mathbf{mp}') = (\mathbf{fmp}' / \mathbf{8}) = \mathbf{0.076882314}$

- $\mathbf{n}^s(\mathbf{mn}') = (\mathbf{fnn}' / \mathbf{5}) = \mathbf{0.076980797}$

In this case, the connection between these values is determined by the difference - the number of the limit of the degree of freedom of these fragments:

- $\mathbf{S}^v = (\mathbf{fmp}' - \mathbf{fnn}') = \mathbf{0.230154527}$

For this value, the unit of charge is also determined:

- $\mathbf{n}^s(\mathbf{s}^v) = [\mathbf{s}^v / (\mathbf{8} - \mathbf{5})] = \mathbf{0.076718176}$

As you can see, the given functional content of the mass number (13) corresponds to the three main values of the cubic structure.

• Mass – Energy

The order of the number of numerical events and number bases ($\mathbf{n}^s = (\mathbf{n}^{-1})$ and $(\mathbf{Ln}(\mathbf{n}))$), of any value, determines the sequence of periods containing and separating equal numerical events of a given number.

This is the linear core composition of the numerical structure of mass. Thus, any numerical structure of a mass number forms within itself a combined composition - a mass system of volumetric and linear periodic values of its content. The number of periods of the composition of the structure of the mass number, to the minus of the first power, corresponds to the binomial - number - field of the number of events in the structure of the square of the mass number: $(n / n^{-1}) = n^2$.

Therefore, one mass number can have any number of numerical events depending on the negative power projection number. Multiple periodic conditions of numerical events, given mass number projections, determine the "shadow" values of these mass definitions, known as "dark" matter - "invisible" matter organized by the boundaries of the mass number contour - matter having no mass - matter combining external and internal energy of communication of the entire Global Space.

Thus, the larger the mass number, the smaller its projection in space - the “longer” the composition of the periodic connection between “visible” and “invisible” matter. And vice versa, the lower the mass number, the “shorter” the composition and the greater the connection between these projections of matter.

For the “apparent” determination of the static and functional structure of mass, without the conditions of projections of “dark” matter, the usual arithmetic opposite operations are used, subtraction - subtraction of the base number of the event and addition - addition of the reduced number of the mass number event. In this case, the projection of the mass number, to the minus of the first power, determines the number of periods of reorientation of the structure of the mass number. Whereas, twice the number of these periods determines the cycle of maintaining the contour of the space of a given mass.

Thus, ($\frac{1}{2}$) part of the periodic cycle of the main content of the mass number corresponds to the process of reorientation of the structure of the composition of the event number, due to which the main determination of the entire functional content of the mass number.

The second half of the cycle, in these periods of reorientation, corresponds to a static unit. Difference of reorientation arguments - event number, sum of reorientation arguments - reduced event number, addition of cycles - determination or conservation of mass number, **Table 1**.

Table 1

Quantitative content of cycle structure			
proton rest mass: $m_p = 1.00727647$			
N	Periods	Periods	Result
X	reorientation	projections	event number
1	1.000000000	-1.001029250	-0.001029250
2	0.992723530	-0.993752780	-0.001029250
	$\frac{1}{4}$ cycle	projections	event number
69	0.505200040	-0.506229290	-0.001029250
70	0.497923570	-0.498952820	-0.001029250
	$\frac{1}{2}$ cycle	projections	event number
138	0.0031236100	-0.004152860	-0.001029250
139	-0.004152860	0.003123610	-0.001029250
	$\frac{3}{4}$ cycle	projections	event number
207	-0.498952820	0.497923570	-0.001029250
208	-0.506229290	0.505200040	-0.001029250
	Cycle	projections	event number
276	-1.001029250	1.000000000	-0.001029250
277	-1.008305720	1.007276470	-0.001029250
278	-1.015582190	1.014552940	-0.001029250

As can be seen from **Table 1**, the main reorientation (X) of the numerical structure of the proton mass number in periods [138 X 139] leads to polar arguments for the position of the displacement in the structure of the event number:

$$\bullet n^s = m_p - (m_p - 1) = 0.00727647$$

Where: $(n^s)^{-1} = 138.4292755$, that is, between periods of reorientation, in the percentage of projections: 43%, in the one hundred and thirty-eighth period, and in the one hundred and thirty-ninth: - 57%. This is in one case. In the case where the event number is a functional value, its definition will form the basis of the mass number, in particular: $(n^s = \text{Ln}(m_p))$.

Then, for further information, the number of numerical events in the proton mass structure will be different: $(m_p / \text{Ln}(m_p) = 138.9323051)$.

The sequence of the general process of reorientation of the complete cycle of doubled periods [138] and [139] leads to the formation of a third odd period [277] with a neutral argument of the negative number of the reduced neutron: $mn' = -1.008305720$.

This definition is according to the binomial of protons in the sum proton – neutron:

$$\bullet (mn + mp) - (mn - mp) = 2mp$$

This is the external field of the cyclic structure of a static proton, as a limit to the order of composition of a sequence of natural numbers: **1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9**.

Here's the static number of the event nine cubed: $n^s (9^3)^{-1} = 0.001371742$.

Whereas, twice the cube of nine approaches the number of all known isotopes of chemical elements: $2(9^3) = 1458$.

Naturally, the “counter” number of isobars is the same: **1458**.

In turn, the event number of this quantity will correspond to the base of the mass content of the functional proton or the base of the square root of the ratio of the static masses of the proton and neutron:

$$\bullet [\exp(1458^{-1})]^2 = 1.001372683$$

$$\bullet 1.001372683 \cdot mp = mn'(1.008659142)$$

Thus, periodic orders of the static composition of the proton mass form a cyclic interaction $\square$ - a structural connection of numerical events, sum limits and differences in the structure of one number of proton mass events. The “merger” of this interaction of a cyclic formation occurs due to periods of reorientation, as a result of which a displacement occurs that distributes the limits of the polar arguments of the composition of the structure of the cyclic charge.

• Charge

Proton

The functional process of reorientation (**X**) of the periodic mass system of any numerical contour forms a conical shape around the empirical axis of the spiral interaction of periodic numerical projections, opposite fragments of the event number composition. As a result, the opposite limits of the maximum interactions of counter cones, from the central axial periods of reorientation (**X**), correspond to the initial and final phase of the interaction of functional fragments of the event number, the reduced mass number. Thus, the vertices of the cones are in direct connection with polar variable values during periods of structural reorientation (**X**).

In this case, two polar outer contour circles of the poles of the general cycle of mass number content are formed, which determine the charge value ($z^{(+/-)}$) of the entire numerical structure of the formed mass, (Data in **Table 1**).

- Positive structure set: **0.00312361**

Period: [1], mp = 1.00727647

Period: [138], 0.00312361

- Result of reorientation of the functional structure of the proton

Period: [139], - 0.00415286

Period: [276], mp' - 0.99375278

- Negative structure set: - **0.00415286**

From the data in Table 1, it follows that reorientation occurs in the structure of the unit, between periods [138] and [139]: $(139 - 138) = 1$.

The sum of the reorientation arguments is the negative number of the event, the second half of the total cycle of the proton mass content, as the number of the reduced event: $(- 0.00415286 + 0.00312361) = - 0.001029250$.

Naturally, the difference in the reorientation arguments will correspond to the positive number of the proton static mass event.

The interaction of polar charge structures occurs due to the periodic composition of these values in the circuit condition of the “**Proton charge modulus matrix**”, where each successive number of the composition is an argument of one period.

The data for the main result of the reorientation of the static proton are in columns; **A** and **B**, periodic compositions: **A(000312361)**, **B(-4,-1,-5,-2,-8,-6)**.

The sum of the arguments of the horizontal periods: **AB4**, **AB5**, **AB6**, **AB7**, **AB8**, **AB9** will be: **AB4 = -1**, **AB5 = 0**, **AB6 = -3**, **AB7 = -1**, **AB8 = -2**, **AB9 = -5**, which forms negative event number: $(- 0.00103125)$, the total sum of all twelve arguments: **- 10**.

Proton charge modulus matrix									
dynamics of the reorientation process									
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	3	-4	2	-5	4	-3	1	-5	-7
5	1	-1	1	-1	1	-1	7	-5	2
6	2	-5	2	-5	2	-5	3	-4	-10
7	3	-2	3	-2	3	-2	5	-1	7
8	6	-8	6	-8	6	-8	0	-4	-10
9	1	-6	1	-6	1	-6	6	0	-9

Further, for example, in the function of **Table 1**, instead of the number of the static proton event, an arbitrary number is entered that changes the value of the fourth period, replacing the number seven with eight, that is, it was (0.00727647) - it became (0.00827647). Thus, a new result of adding arguments appeared in columns C and D:

$CD4 = -3$, $CD5 = 0$, $CD6 = -3$, $CD7 = -1$, $CD8 = -2$, $CD9 = -5$, by number: - 0.00303125.

In this case, the sum of the twelve arguments given is: -12.

Next, entering the event number: ns (0.00627647), the result of columns E and F, leads to a number whose structure contains a “conflict” of charge polarization in the overall composition of the sum of arguments: (- 0.00097075).

In this case, the sum: $E4 + F4 = 1$, that is, equal to a positive number. Whereas, the remaining amounts of this composition are negative.

These examples were not taken by chance. Replacing the number 7, the fourth period, with a larger number 8, this period, leads the entire set of arguments to a negative value for the number of the event in the period of reorientation.

In the case when the argument of the fourth period is replaced by a number of a smaller value, then the argument of this period changes its sign to the opposite.

Then, the sums of the arguments **AB4** and **EF4** will be:

(- 0.00103125) and (- 0.00097075), provided that the other arguments are equal.

In contrast to the sum of the twelve arguments of the **AB** columns, which is equal to (- 10), the sum of the twelve arguments of the **EF** columns is already equal to (- 8). That is, reducing the period number by one results in a difference in amounts of two units.

The diagram, “**Static structure of the arguments for the reorientation of the proton charge**”, shows the principle of the distribution, periodic compositions of the interaction of numerical events of the proton mass.

The following example, in columns **G** and **H**, demonstrates the input of a static neutron event number, "**Proton Charge Modulus Matrix**", into the static proton structure, with the results of numerical reorientation events.

These are: $G n^s = 0.001735068$ and $H n^s = -0.005541402$. Sum: $n^s (0.003806336)$.

Looking ahead, it should be said that the average number of this sum: -0.001903167, corresponds to the real number of the Helium ${}_2\text{He}^4$ neutron projection event.

The sum of twelve arguments of columns **G** and **H**, the matrix of the proton charge modulus, will be: 3, with an average number: (0.25). The structure of the matrix of the proton charge module is completed by column **I**, containing the sums of horizontal periods: **1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9**, the vertical sum of which will be: (- 27), with the number of six arguments and the average number: (4.5)

The given characteristics determine the dynamic moment of counter processes of reorientation of the functional structure of the proton charge.

This moment corresponds to the state of the composition of the structure, its ratio of interactions of polar bond arguments within the limits of charge orientation.

Neutron

The rationale proposed by the author for describing the “transition” functions of Mössbauer nuclei, in early case studies, reveals a well-known defect for a broader definition of the interactions of protons and neutrons in the composition of nucleons - charge units, not only of mother and daughter nuclei, but also for modulation of the “cold” nuclear synthesis.

As can be seen from the content of the cycle of the quantitative structure of the mass of a static proton (**Table 1**), the periods of the reorientation contour limits: (1 – 277), determine the main values of charge formation by the reduced numbers of the proton and neutron: $mn' = (-1.008305720)$ and ($mp = 1.007276470$). In the case of reorientation of a static neutron, the binary cycle of the content of the structure is completed by its mass number (**Table 2**).

Here, too, it should be said for the future that the event number obtained as a result of the sum of arguments, the reorientation of the numerical structure of the mass number of the static neutron, in periods 116 and 117, corresponds to the event number, the reduced mass number of the Nitrogen neutron ${}^7N^{14}$, in the final period 232.

Thus, an opportunity is provided for a comparative analysis of the polarized structures of the proton and neutron charges in the nucleon, the diagram “**General structure of the arguments for the reorientation of the proton and neutron charges**”.

Proton – neutron

The matrix of this combined structure, the polar arguments of the periods of reorientation of the proton and neutron, determines these values, in the form of horizontal and vertical sums of the arguments of the composition: “**Matrix of the modulus and sum of the charges of the neutron and proton**”.

Matrix of the modulus and sum of the charges									
of the neutron nnd proton									
Dynamic processes of reorientation									
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	0	0	0	0					
2	0	0	0	0					
3	0	0	0	0					
4	3	-5	3	-4					-3
5	5	-1	1	-1					4
6	2	-4	2	-5					-5
7	3	-1	3	-2					3
8	6	-3	6	-8					1
9	2	-9	1	-6					-12
J	21	-23	16	-26	-12	Sum			-12

Here, columns **AB** correspond to the periods of content of the composition of the arguments for the reorientation of the structure of the mass number of the static neutron. In turn, the **CD** columns correspond to the content of the arguments for the reorientation of the structure of the mass number of the static proton. Column **I** defines the sums of the horizontal arguments of the matrix structure. Column **J** defines the sums of the vertical arguments of the matrix structure.

The characteristic content of structural definitions of mass compositions is the law of conservation of mass number within any limits of polar reorientation arguments. In other words, each mass number contains information from any mass numbers as part of its periodic structure. This occurs by determining the real numbers of the proton and neutron in the nucleon. In this case, the reorientation process, which determines the key periods of polarization of charges containing or forming any mass number, does not correspond to the traditional concepts of adding or subtracting mass numbers. The functions that determine the mass contents of structural periodic compositions are within the internal and external contents of the mass numerical system. Thus, each mass number structure definition can be represented as a "compression" function or an "expansion" function.

For example, the mass number consisting of the number of **A** protons and the number of **B** protons refers to these compounds as the act of the "expansion" phase:

- $[(A+B) / A]$ and $[(A+B) / B]$, whereas: $[(A+B) \times A]$ and $[(A+B) \times B] \rightarrow$ act of the "compression" phase.

Naturally, the ratio of the acts of "compression" and "expansion" to the sum of the proton and neutron will be: $n \leftrightarrow n^{-1}$, since the sum of the static projections of these definitions: $[(A+B) / A]^{-1} \leftrightarrow [(A+B) / B]^{-1}$ and $[(A+B) \times A]^{-1} \leftrightarrow [(A+B) \times B]^{-1}$ will be equal to one.

In the case when there is a shift in the ratio of the mass number compositions, which is determined by the number of the nucleon, equal or not equal to one, then the interaction of the projections of the mass number composition acquires a functional significance.

For example, from the material "Introduction" of this text it follows that the Oxygen nucleon:

- $nykl O^{16} \rightarrow (15.9994 / 16) = 0.9999625.$

Thus, each projection is a functional part of the mass number, participates in the distribution of the content of the mass structure within the given processes of “expansion” or “compression”, “capture” or “emission” of the product of functional interactions, “thermal” or “cold” expression numerical mass system.

For example, by the mass of Oxygen ${}_8\text{O}^{16}$, its nucleon: $\text{nykl } {}_8\text{O}^{16} = 0.9999625$.

Projection phase of the proton function: $\text{fmp} = [(A+B) / A]^{-1} = 0.49965561$.

Neutron function projection phase: $\text{fnn} = (\text{nykl } {}_8\text{O}^{16} - \text{fmp}) = 0.50030689$.

Next, the event number, or mass unit: $\mathbf{n}^S = (16^{-1}) = 0.0625$.

Then: $\text{fmp} / \mathbf{n}^S = \text{number of protons} \rightarrow \text{nmp}' = 7.994489753$.

$\text{fnn} / \mathbf{n}^S = \text{number of neutrons} \rightarrow \text{fnn}' = 8.004910247$.

After which, we determine the real functional numbers of protons and neutrons:

$\text{mp}' = (\mathbf{n}^{\text{mp}'}) / 8 = 0.999311219$; $\text{mn}' = (\mathbf{n}^{\text{mn}'}) / 8 = 1.000613781$.

The degree of “transition” (S^n), number – number field, in this case, will be:

$$S^n = \text{Ln}(\mathbf{n}^{\text{mn}'}) / \text{Ln}(\mathbf{n}^{\text{mp}'}) = - 0.890531781$$

This is what the proton exchange phase is all about: $\text{fmp} = [(A+B) / A]^{-1} = 0.49965561$.

In the case of the neutron phase, the value of the real number of the proton will be the “inverse” of the number of the proton phase, that is, to the minus of the first power, while the number of the neutron will be different.

Neutron exchange phase: $[(A+B) / B]^{-1} = 0.50034439$

In both cases, the reorientation processes will be different. The coordination of these functions determines and separates the organic and inorganic structures of matter. But, in general, in both cases, the value of the mass number can be any for a given topic. This is due to the opposing orders of composition of protons and neutrons in mass numbers. Whereas, the main determination of a specific mass structure is the number of the established nucleon. For comparison, let us introduce into the functional structure of the same Oxygen (${}_8\text{O}^{16}$) any mass number of its isotopes. For example, the mass number is twenty. Then, the ratio of proton functions to neutron functions in this structure will be eight to twelve.

Therefore, the numbers of these arguments will be different:

Proton phase of functional exchange: $\mathbf{fmp}[(8\mathbf{mp}+12\mathbf{mn})/8\mathbf{mp}]^{-1} = 0.399669431$

Functional neutron projection: $\mathbf{fmn} = (\mathbf{nykl} \text{ } {}_8\mathbf{O}^{20} - \mathbf{fmp}) = 0.600293069$

Determination of proton composition: $\mathbf{nmp} = \mathbf{fmp} / (20^{-1}) = 7.993388614$

Determination of neutron composition: $\mathbf{nmn} = \mathbf{fmp} / (20^{-1}) = 12.00586139$

Determination of the real number of a proton: $\mathbf{mp}' = \mathbf{n}^{\mathbf{mp}} / 8 = 0.999173577$

Determination of the real number of a neutron: $\mathbf{mn}' = \mathbf{n}^{\mathbf{mn}} / 12 = 1.000488449$

In this case, the “field” of the proton number carries the information of the root of the square number of the neutron of the “mirror” nucleus of Nitrogen ${}_7\mathbf{N}^{14}$:

$$\mathbf{mn}'({}_7\mathbf{N}^{14}) = {}_8\mathbf{O}^{20} (\mathbf{mp}'^{-1})^2 = 1.001654898$$

In turn, the neutron of Oxygen ${}_8\mathbf{O}^{20}$ is the number of the nucleon of Nitrogen, then its mass is:

$$\mathbf{m}({}_7\mathbf{N}^{14}) = 14\mathbf{mn}'({}_8\mathbf{O}^{20}) = 14.00683828$$

From which it follows that the proton of the “mirror” isotope of Nitrogen ${}_7\mathbf{N}^{14}$ will be:

$$\mathbf{mp}'({}_7\mathbf{N}^{14}) = [\mathbf{m}({}_7\mathbf{N}^{14}) - 7\mathbf{mn}'({}_7\mathbf{N}^{14})] / 7 = 0.999322$$

Its numerical and functional correction coincides with the functional number of protons of all mirror nuclei. In the process of expansion of primary Hydrogen, due to the function of reducing its charge, the first stable element in this structure is Oxygen (${}_8\mathbf{O}^{16}$). After it is Nitrogen (${}_7\mathbf{N}^{14}$), followed by Helium (${}_2\mathbf{He}^4$), then Carbon (${}_6\mathbf{C}^{12}$) - data from the author’s mathematical cyclic table.

In this case, it should be said that the order of any composition of mass definitions depends on the conditions of the functional definitions of specific content and the selection of one or another value, argument of the numerical structure in the mass system. The principle of the so-called “sorting” of ordinal compositions is of a defining nature, specific functional values isolated from the general structure of the mass system, which determines the various categories of numerical data.

Table 3 is a fragment of a cyclic mathematical table of the order of chemical elements relative to the number of neutrons.

Table 3.

N	z	el	m ⁿ	n	m
61	8	<i>O</i>	16	1	15.9994
62	7	<i>N</i>	14	2	14.0067
63	2	<i>He</i>	4	3	4.0026
64	6	<i>C</i>	12	4	12.011
65	16	<i>S</i>	32	5	32.06
66	20	<i>Ca</i>	40	6	40.08
67	19	<i>K</i>	38	10	0
68	14	<i>Si</i>	28	7	28.0855
69	30	<i>Zn</i>	60	22	0
70	10	<i>Ne</i>	20	8	20.179
71	32	<i>Ge</i>	65	31	0
72	29	<i>Cu</i>	59	24	0
73	31	<i>Ga</i>	63	28	0
74	28	<i>Ni</i>	57	15	0
75	12	<i>Mg</i>	24	9	24.305

And so, the peculiarity of the “limit” of the numerical structure of the Oxygen isotope (${}_8\text{O}^{20}$) is associated with three main arguments in the process of reorientation.

These are the proton function number, the neutron function number and the degree of freedom number (S^v) - the functional difference between the arguments of the proton and neutron. As can be seen from the result of determining the functional arguments of the proton and neutron (${}_8\text{O}^{20}$), the numbers of proton and neutron fragments in the composition of the Oxygen nucleon correspond to:

▪ $\mathbf{fmp}' = 0.399669431$ and $\mathbf{fmn}' = 0.600293069$.

The degree of freedom of these definitions will be: $S^v = \mathbf{fmp}' - \mathbf{fmn}' = - 0.200628759$.

A negative number. That is, a shift to the “cold” phase.

In the case of the other extreme limit of the number of the nucleon of Oxygen, its isotope (${}_8\text{O}^{13}$), set out in the text “Introduction”, this material, the number of functional arguments of the proton and neutron are the following values:

$\mathbf{fmp} = 0.615058513$ and $\mathbf{fmn} = 0.384903987$, the degree of freedom of which will be:

$$S^v = \mathbf{fmp} - \mathbf{fmn} = 0.230154526.$$

Positive number. That is, a shift to the “hot” phase. Extreme isotopes are the limits of charges when the argument of one function approaches $\frac{1}{2}$ of the argument of the second function. Otherwise, the number of degrees of freedom will be equal to one of the functional arguments of the nucleon composition. The known instability of the extreme isotopes of all nuclear symbols is associated with the activity of the interconnection and transitions of mass numbers among themselves in the functional structure of general Matter. In this case, in the structure of each nucleon there is a reorientation of its functional arguments in the range of degrees of freedom **Table 4**.

Table 4.

N	fmp	fmn	S ^v	m ⁿ	m ⁻¹	n (mp)	n (mn)	m	mp'	mn'
1	0.615059	0.384904	-0.23015	13	0.076923	7.995761	5.003752	12.99951	0.9994701	1.0007504
2	0.571091	0.428871	-0.14222	14	0.071429	7.995276	6.004199	13.99948	0.9994096	1.0006998
3	0.53299	0.466972	-0.06602	15	0.066667	7.994857	7.004581	14.99944	0.9993571	1.0006544
4	0.499656	0.500307	0.000651	16	0.0625	7.99449	8.00491	15.9994	0.9993112	1.0006138
5	0.470245	0.529717	0.059472	17	0.058824	7.994166	9.005197	16.99936	0.9992707	1.0005774
6	0.444104	0.555858	0.111754	18	0.055556	7.993878	10.00545	17.99933	0.9992347	1.0005447
7	0.420717	0.579246	0.158529	19	0.052632	7.99362	11.00567	18.99929	0.9992026	1.0005152
8	0.399669	0.600293	0.200624	20	0.05	7.993389	12.00586	19.99925	0.9991736	1.0004884

Table 4. Reorientation between 15 and 16 mass numbers of Oxygen isotopes. The positions of functional arguments 13 and 20 mass numbers are swapped. All real numbers of protons (*mp'*) of Oxygen isotopes are a projection of the numbers of neutrons (*mn'*).

In complex definitions of mass systems, as well as hypothetically, options for studying “transcendental” formations of mass structures of nuclear symbols are possible. These formations are of an informational computational nature for data obtained as a result of the processes of “compression” of mass complexes and their “expansion”, when it is necessary to determine the result of a numerical “synthesis”. The fact is that the defining, real “neutron”, from the point of view of the content of the functional mass structure, is the argument of the degree of freedom - a substance located in a “continuous” neutral phase of exchange, containing within itself a formed multi-polar composition of opposite functional values as a result interaction of arguments of phase limits of opposite charges of protons and neutrons in nucleon compositions. These counter and opposite “neutral poses” of interaction of functional limits, in the process of reorientation, are the main material for the formation of “new” nuclei that are not part of the information composition of known functional symbols. At the same time, hypothetically, theoretically, and not only, they have the possibility of any logical content within the limits of the numbers of nucleons. For example, variants of the functional structures of unknown Oxygen isotopes, **Tables 5** and **6**.

Table 5.

N	fmp'	fmn'	S ^v	m ⁿ	m ⁻¹	n (mp')	n (mn')	m'	mp'	mn'
1	0.888753	0.11121	0.777543	9	0.111111	7.998775	1.000888	8.999663	0.999847	1.000888
2	0.799779	0.200183	0.599596	10	0.1	7.997795	2.00183	9.999625	0.999724	1.000915
3	0.726999	0.272963	0.454036	11	0.090909	7.996993	3.002594	10.99959	0.999624	1.000865
4	0.66636	0.333602	0.332758	12	0.083333	7.996326	4.003224	11.99955	0.999541	1.000806

Table 6.

N	fmp'	fmn'	S ^v	m ⁿ	m ⁻¹	n (mp)	n (mn)	m'	mp'	mn'
1	0.380628	0.619335	-0.23871	21	0.047619	7.993179	13.00603	20.99921	0.999147	1.000464
2	0.363318	0.636645	-0.27333	22	0.045455	7.992988	14.00619	21.99918	0.999124	1.000442
3	0.347514	0.652449	-0.30494	23	0.043478	7.992814	15.00632	22.99914	0.999102	1.000422
4	0.333027	0.666935	-0.33391	24	0.041667	7.992655	16.00645	23.9991	0.999082	1.000403
5	0.3197	0.680262	-0.36056	25	0.04	7.992508	17.00655	24.99906	0.999063	1.000386
6	0.307399	0.692564	-0.38516	26	0.038462	7.992372	18.00665	25.99903	0.999047	1.00037
7	0.296009	0.703953	-0.40794	27	0.037037	7.992247	19.00674	26.99899	0.999031	1.000355
8	0.285433	0.714529	-0.4291	28	0.035714	7.992131	20.00682	27.99895	0.999016	1.000341
9	0.275587	0.724376	-0.44879	29	0.034483	7.992022	21.00689	28.99891	0.999003	1.000328
10	0.266397	0.733565	-0.46717	30	0.033333	7.991921	22.00695	29.99888	0.99899	1.000316
11	0.257801	0.742162	-0.48436	31	0.032258	7.991826	23.00701	30.99884	0.998978	1.000305
12	0.249742	0.750221	-0.50048	32	0.03125	7.991737	24.00706	31.9988	0.998967	1.000294
13	0.242171	0.757791	-0.51562	33	0.030303	7.991654	25.00711	32.99876	0.998957	1.000284
14	0.235046	0.764916	-0.52987	34	0.029412	7.991576	26.00715	33.99873	0.998947	1.000275
15	0.228329	0.771634	-0.54331	35	0.028571	7.991502	27.00719	34.99869	0.998938	1.000266

The contents of tables 5 and 6 refer to the structure of one general number - the number of the Oxygen nucleon, which contains all its known and unknown isotopes. **Table 5** shows the functional structures from the ninth to the twelfth mass. **Table 5** shows the result of a strong bias in the limit of the proton function in the (fmp') column of the Oxygen isotope (${}_8\text{O}^9$). Whereas, the result of the limit of the neutron function, in column (fmn'), is practically equal to the number of the mass number event, columns (mn) and (m⁻¹).

In turn, the columns for the number of protons and neutrons (n(mp')) and (n(mn')) confirm this trend. Column (m') determines the reduced mass number of the Oxygen isotope. The critical shift of the proton function ends with the twelfth mass isotope of Oxygen. Further, up to the twenty-first mass of this element, there will be eight known isotopes. From the twenty-first mass to the thirty-fifth, a critical shift begins towards the proton function, **Table 6**. In both cases, the sum of the functional arguments of the proton and neutron will be equal to the number of the Oxygen nucleon.

Returning to the interaction of the functions of the proton and neutron in the structure of the nucleon charge unit, we should consider in detail, using the example of reorientations of these real numbers in the process of their own reorientation. For example, the functional number of the proton and the functional number of the neutron of the Oxygen isotope (${}_8\text{O}^{16}$) change the polarity of their structures in different periods. It is characteristic that the reorientation of the functional structure of the proton occurs “before” the reorientation of the functional structure of the neutron, **Table 7**.

Table 7.

Neutron reorientation ${}_8\text{O}^{16}$				Proton reorientation ${}_8\text{O}^{16}$			
N^P	X	n^S	X/n^S	N^P	X	n^S	X/n^S
1631	0.00045765786	0.00061359271	0.7458658643	1451	0.000234657	-0.000689018	-0.340567207
1632	-0.0001559349	0.00061359271	-0.2541341357	1452	-0.000454361	-0.000689018	0.659432793

Here, the value of the number (N^P) of the positive limit (0.00045765786) of the period (1631) of neutron reorientation is polar to the value of the negative limit (-0.000454361) of the number (N^P) of the period (1452) of proton reorientation. The values of the arguments for the interaction of the proton and neutron functions are determined by the ratio of the reorientation number (X) to the event number (n^S), where the event number is the base of the proton or neutron number: $n^S = L_n(n)$. In this case, the result arguments set the displacements of the proton and neutron functions neutrons in the reduced charge structure.

For comparison, (X/n^S), neutron reorientation (${}_8\text{O}^{16}$), **Table 7**, orients the approximate state, for comparison, between the masses of Oxygen isotopes, in the columns: (fmn') $fm'({}_8\text{O}^{31-32})$ and (S^V) (${}_8\text{O}^{21-22}$), **Table 6**. Naturally, these values are of an informational nature related to the determination of numerical values obtained as a result of functional formations.

In particular, in the case of **Table 7**, the comparative “poses” of the columns (X/n^S) determine the state of “compression” and “expansion” of the limits of the proton and neutron charge structures. As can be seen from these data, the charge state of the neutron is critical, in contrast to the state of the proton.

As in the case of arguments for the content of the modulus of periodic matrices, it should be said that the interaction of a proton and a neutron is not in the same periodic order of numerical events. They cannot be added like regular numbers.

These arguments are independent of each other and are not in a constant numerical expression of counter and opposite functional periodic structures of numerical events. Only functions of the numerical structure of mass - energy are constant.

Consequently, the sequences for counting the periodicity of the compositions of the functional processes of proton and neutron reorientation will be counter and opposite (like palindrome numbers).

The combination or interaction of the charges of a proton and a neutron, located in their own cycles of periodic functional structures, forms a binary general cycle ($\square$) of the total charge, the structure of which is in a variable state between the limits of the functional values of the internal and external content of the structure of space, formed mass - energy.

For example, nucleons “pose” the “expansion” of the neutron and proton:

- $\text{nykl}^{\text{mm}'}(\text{x} / \text{n}^{\text{s}}) = 0.7458658642716840 - (-0.2541341357283160) = 1$

- $\text{nykl}^{\text{mp}'}(\text{x} / \text{n}^{\text{s}}) = -0.3405672067376680 - 0.6594327932623320 = -1$

Nucleons “pose” “compression” of the neutron and proton:

- $\text{nykl}^{\text{mm}'}(\text{x} / \text{n}^{\text{s}}) = 0.7458658642716840 + (-0.2541341357283160) = 0.4917317285433690$

- $\text{nykl}^{\text{mp}'}(\text{x} / \text{n}^{\text{s}}) = -0.3405672067376680 + 0.6594327932623320 = 0.318865246650$

As can be seen from the data, the state of charge interaction, within the “expansion” phases of the proton and neutron structure, is within the structures of one and minus one. The limits of "compression" determine the degree of functional structure of the positive displacement. The state of the cyclic structure of the charge of interaction between a proton and a neutron is determined by the sum of the opposing polar limits of the arguments of the reorientation periods (nykl^{e}):

- $\text{nykl}^{\text{e}} = ({}_{1631}\text{x} / \text{n}^{\text{s}}) + ({}_{1451} \text{x} / \text{n}^{\text{s}}) = 0.4052986'359791720$

- $\text{nykl}^{\text{e}} = ({}_{1632}\text{x} / \text{n}^{\text{s}}) + ({}_{1452} \text{x} / \text{n}^{\text{s}}) = 0.4052986'575340160$

As already mentioned, this data is for informational purposes only and is not included in the content of this topic. It should only be said that the results obtained in the process of presenting this text can be presented as accompanying studies for other studies based on the existing database.

For example, the information contained in **Table 6**, in columns:

(fmn') $fm'({}_8O^{31-32})$ and (S^v) $({}_8O^{21-22})$, corresponds to two elements:

${}_{31}Ga^{63}(fmp) = nykl\ mn'(X/n^s) = 0.4917317285433690$ and ${}_{21}Sc^{43}(fmp) = 0.488027894$.

Information of the limits of the arguments of the reorientation periods:

$(nykl^e) = 0.4052986'$, refers to the state (fmp) ${}_{79}Au^{195}$.

Determination of the functional relationship of the charges of the proton and neutron, as a structure of the nucleon composition, which is in the process of reorientation, when the arguments of the interaction of the numbers of events are in the phase of the “compression” limits, that is, they tend to reorientation, creating a periodic conical structure of the mass structure. Their function is directed into the content of the formation of the mass system. In turn, the interaction of the effective arguments of the periods of charge reorientation, the given numerical structure, tends to the external expression of the mass of the limits of “expansion”. Thus, the process of “compression”, its transformation of the interaction of charge arguments, one content of the mass functional structure, acquires the reverse process of “expansion”, “growth” of a new structure of charge arguments of the reduced composition of the numerical mass.

• Time – Dark Matter

The periodic sequence of counter orders of natural numbers: **123456789** ↔ **987654321**, from the point of view of palindrome numbers, elementary mathematics, form a countable matrix of periodic limits of each numerical order, the sum of which will be equal to ten periods: **123456789 + 987654321 = 1111111110**. The difference of these orders will constitute a “chaotic order”, which determines the value of opposing periodic limits relative to each other.

In this case: **987654321 – 123456789 = 864197532**, for spatial structural definitions, the difference of opposing numerical orders forms a cycle (□) of two compositions containing numerical levels, due to reorientation within one and nine.

As can be seen from the result of the difference in counter orders, all numbers remain within the limit of a nine-digit composition, in the center of which is the number of period nine and the number of the first period shifted to the left. Thus, the left side, relative to the central number nine, contains the order of periods: **8641**.

The right side, relative to the central number nine, contains the order: 7532. In the first case, three numbers: 864 are even. In the second case: 753 are odd. The general composition of the difference of counter orders: 864197532, contains even numbers at the beginning and end of the outer periods of the number structure. The internal content of this order is determined by odd numbers.

The ratio of these values in the spatial structure of the periodic contour will be: 864 (53%); 753 (47%).

The definition of the numerical sequence, from left to right and from right to left - back and forth, does not correspond to the order of the percentage due to the periodic limits of the numerical values of the increase and decrease of the counter numerical compositions. That is, the order of the “internal” count: 123456789 and the order of the “external” count: 987654321, in percentage functional terms, will be: 11% ↔ 89%. From the point of view of the category of time, the time of events of order: 123456789 will be less than the time of events of order: 987654321 by 8.090909091 times.

This is the law of the conditions of the functional structure of the primary volume ($\pi/6$), consisting of numerical projections of two limits of unit periods: $\boxed{1} \boxed{1}$. Here, the case when the periodic value of the numerical composition determines the projection of its content in the “reflected cycle” of a given sequence.

In this case: $(8.090909091 - 8)^{-1} = 11$.

Here: $[2 + 3 + 6] = 11$; $[2^{-1} + 3^{-1} + 6^{-1}] = 1$ (!)

The superposition of time vectors creates a confusion of time with a subsequent violation of the ordinal composite structures of successive periodic values. In turn, the mixed order of the composition of periods projects its content in the matrix of space as dark matter - the order of the “conflict” of space outside of time (**Matrix 1**).

Matrix 1.

-	t→									←t	+
1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	9	
2										8	
3										7	
4	1	3	5	8	0	2	4	6	7	6	
5	8	6	4	1	9	7	5	3	2	5	
6	7	2	8	3	9	5	0	6	5	4	
7										3	
8										2	
9	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	1	
+	t→									←t	-

Matrix 1. Periodic composition of mixed vector time of counter orders of natural numbers: (864197532), forming projections of dark matter orders: (135802467) and their differences: (728395065).

This definition refers to the constant functional of communication between material and immaterial Space.

• Conclusion

And so – limits! Limits are positive and negative compounds that form any structure of numbers. The limits that form the cycle are the type of content and manifestation of mass - energy as a material substance in the Space of Matter. In a well-known case, the existing intelligence of consciousness and perception of the material World with digital definitions and differences, formed objects of phenomena and their manifestations located in the system of Global Interaction, in the form of the Law of Conservation of Mass, elementary and periodic, external and internal content, located within these limits - limits numbers of a mathematical cyclic table of all known and unknown isotopes of nuclear symbols.

All local content of the material space of the cyclic table is within the functional structure of the nucleon of Helium isotopes: $\left| {}_2\text{He}^3 \leftrightarrow \square \leftrightarrow {}_2\text{He}^8 \right|$.

• Related materials

▪ Based on the author's material:

- [Functional structure of mathematical physics \(zenodo.org\)](https://zenodo.org/)
- [Basic Functions of the Numerical Structure of Scientific Data \(zenodo.org\)](https://zenodo.org/)
- <https://www.internauka.org/journal/science/internauka/89>

[“THE MATHEMATICAL TABLE OF CHEMICAL SYMBOLS” \(page. 35\)](#)

[“THE GRAVITATIONAL STRUCTURE OF THE DEGREE OF MOTION OF THE FUNCTIONAL COMPOSITION OF THE VOLUME OF TIME, PHASE CYCLES OF THE BASIC FUNCTIONS OF SPACE” \(page 45\)](#)

- [https://internauka.org/archive2/internauka/6\(88_2\).pdf](https://internauka.org/archive2/internauka/6(88_2).pdf)

[“THE CAUSES AND CONDITIONS OF THE FORMATION OF THE FUNCTIONAL STRUCTURE OF HYDROGEN” \(page. 31\)](#)

- **Thematic sources of information:**

- [New Trends in Mathematical Physics](#)

Selected contributions of the XVth International Congress on Mathematical Physics
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- [Simonetta Liuti](#)

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